

Review of Effect of *Marica* on *Shitapitta*

Dr. Mrs. Vedashri A. Kalavade¹, Dr. Satish S.Chapadgaonkar²,
Dr. Swarup P. Kulkarni³, Dr. Priyanka Hanmane⁴

¹Associate Professor, ²Professor and H.O.D, Dept. of Rognidan Vikruti Vidnyan,

³Associate Professor and H.O.D. Dept. of Sharir Rachana, ⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa,
Dr.J.J.Magadum Ayu. Medical College, Jaysingpur. Maharashtra, India

Corresponding Author: Dr. Mrs. Vedashri A. Kalavade

ABSTRACT

Shitapitta Udarda, Kotha are the types of skin disorders mentioned in Ayu.samhitas. These can be correlated with Urticaria in modern science. Actually these are three separate disorders to ayu. samhitas. Burning sensation & itching all over the body is cardinal symptom present in these disorders. Skin eruptions are also seen.

Marica i.e. Piper nigrum is very much effective in Shitapitta Udarda Kotha. Marica i.e. BlackPepper is a plant of Piperaceae family. As mentioned in Ayurved taste (rasa) of Maica is Katu (pungent) and .qualities of this are rooksha (dry), and potency is Hot (ushna). Post digestion effect (Vipaka) is katu (pungent

Pipera nigrum i.e. Marica is abortifacient, anthelmintic. It is stimulant to the skin. All this qualities of Marica make it beneficial in skin disorder.

According to modern pharmacology, Piper nigrum is stimulant carminative, antiasthmatic, stimulant to skin in property.

Key words: *Shitapitta, Udarda, Kotha, Marica.*

INTRODUCTION

Shitapitta is a type of skin disorder mentioned in ayurvedic texts which can be correlated with urticaria in modern sciences. Skin eruptions and all over itching is observed in this disease. Twakdushti is mainly observed. Haridra i.e. curcuma longa due its properties act as Kapha Pitta shamak so can be beneficial in it.

Shitapitta

INTRODUCTION

Shitapitta-Udarda- kotha are allergic disorders mentioned in Ayurvedic Texts. Actually these are three separate disorders. In ayurvedic texts these are mentioned as synonyms. Twakdushti (skin disorder) is seen in Shitapitta ⁽¹⁾

Causes- Aharaj

Consumption of salty (lavana) and pungent (katu) food in excessive manner. Eating of more quantity of sour gruels (arnela & shukta). Excessive intake of food items having hot properties like mustard (sarshapa sevan). ⁽¹⁾

Viharaj

Exposure to cold breeze (shitamarut samsparshat) is the main causative factor which increases the shit property. Contact with cold substances (sheet paneeya samsparsha). Sleeping during day time (deewaswap). Impro[per emesis (asmyak vaman) Altered features in winter and rainy season (shishir –varsha ritu viparyaya) Insect bite (keeta damsha), Krimi samsarga (contact of poisonous insects or bugs) ⁽²⁾

Pathology

All the three doshas (vata, pitta, kapha) are involved according to pathology described in ayurvedic texts. Actually Shita is not the property of pitta. This indicates association of kapha and vata. The word Shita here denotes association of Shita property along with aggravation of Pitta. Pitta is vitiated due to etiological factors i.e. hot, pungent substances. In association with aggravation of pitta, contact with cold breeze circulating all over the body i.e. (both externally and internally) increases, snigdha gun of kapha and ruksha guna (dryness) of vata. ⁽³⁾

Signs and symptoms

Due to this pathology excessive thirst, anorexia, reddishness of eyes, nausea, heaviness in chest are observed as premonitory signs.

Skin eruptions which are elevated resemble like that produced by the sting of wasp, associated with severe itching, pricking pain, burning sensation, fever, vomiting are observed in Shitapitta. ⁽⁴⁾

Kotha

Kotha is the disease resembling the same signs and symptoms of Shitapitta. Differentiating factor is cause. Suppression of emesis produces lesion like Shitapitta known as Kotha.

To pause the pathology one has to suggest drugs having property to decrease Kapha & Vata. Marica i.e. Piper nigrum is the plant from Piperaceae family. English word used for this is Black Pepper. This proves very useful in Shitapitta-Udarda-Kota.

Udarda

If kapha dosha is prominent in the above mentioned pathology then it results to Udarda. Main differentiating factor between Udarda & Shitapitta is presence of itching sensation. It is excessive in Udarda due to vitiation Kapha dosha. In Udarda is elevated, reddish, highly irritating, round patches produced by kapha mainly in Shishir ritu

Modern correlation –This can be correlated with Urticaria according to

modern science. This is a type of allergy or hypersensitivity. Food substances such as fish, non vegetarian food, eggs, commonly known for allergy. Worm infections and some medicines like quinines are also for allergic reaction. ⁽⁵⁾

Marica (Black Pepper) :

Chief characters: Perennial twinner, grows upto 10m height. Leaves are simple, Flowers are green.

Synonyms –Vellaja, Ushna, Krishna, Dharmapattana

Gana-Acharya Charaka has included this in Deepaniya, Shoolaprashamaniya, Krimighna gana. ^[5]

Maharshi Sushruta has included this in Pippalyadi, Tryushana gana (trikatu). ⁽⁶⁾

Properties – Rasa (taste)- Katu(pungent).

Post digestion effect-Katu (Pungent)

Properties-Ruksha(dry)

Action on dosha-Kapha Pitta shamak, Deepana, increases Pitta, ⁽⁷⁾

Parts used fruits

Chemical composition -

Piperine is the main alkaloid found in Indian Long Pepper. Piperine is antipyretic, hypotensive, and central nervous system stimulant.

Pharmacological action-

It works as Smooth muscle relaxant. It can induce abortion. It can reduce or prevent damage to joints. It is anthelmintic and also anti-inflammatory analgesic property in addition to hepatoprotective agents. It promotes production secretion and discharge of bile from the system. It has antidiarrhoeal action. It can be useful in toothache, snake bite. It can produce redness of the skin e.g. by causing dilation of capillaries and an increase in blood circulation. It works as antioxidant and proved as chemopreventive means can prevent growth of cancer. It has some anti bacterial properties. It improves permeability. It improves bioavailability of Rifampicin. ⁽⁸⁾

Uses and action –

External use.- External application on the skin increases heat. Also help in decrease inflammatory swelling. It is useful in abscess. Its action like debridement of doashas. It can be applied in any type of swelling also on the eyes. It can be used in some skin disorders like Shvitra, Kilas, Eczema Psoriasis. It can be used in any type of painful inflammatory joints. It can be used in night blindness, pterygium in eyes. It can be used in toothache. In various types of throat infection gargles can be done .Due to hot potency and also pungent taste it has piercing or, lacinating property which can be used in skin growths and some types of tumors. In comatose patients nasya (snuffing) of the powder of the Marica is advised. ⁽⁹⁾

Internal application

- It is due to hot potency and pungent taste increase salivation and also increases digestive secretions. So it is helpful in decreasing obstruction in strotas also digestion of undigested food i.e. chyme (Ama)
- It is anthelmintic and also work as wormicidal
- Also it is helpful in Dysentery and increases digestive property.
- It increase hepatic capacity, and reduces fatty liver.
- It has specific effect on splenomegaly, hepatitis, Chronic skin disorder
- Inspiratory system also it helps in Diseases like coughing and asthma and bronchitis due to Kaphahar property.
- In urinary system also due to decreasing Kapha and Meda it helps in urinary tract infection and increases quantity of urine.
- Maric is helpful in dysmenorrhoea and amenorrhoea. It is also useful in impotency.
- In chronic types of fever it is helpful due to special capacity to increase the Dhatvagni and also decreasing the Kapha. So, it is the main component of the drugs like Suvarna malini vasant.

- Due to special quality Pramathi it can travel to every small strotas so can reduce the obstruction .Hence it can increase the dhatu ball and hence removes all the sticked doshas in all strotas. ⁽¹⁰⁾

From all above description Marica is very good in dosha shodhan i.e. activates Sweating property i.e. Swedavah strotas activation. It increases perspiration hence it is useful in the diseases like Shitapitta - Udarda Kotha. Due properties decreasing Kapha it acts as Kandughna i.e. decreases itching.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Due to Katu (pungent), hot, tikshna properties of Marica it helps in decreasing Kapha and so very much useful in Shitapitta, Udarda, Kotha. It breaks pathology decreasing kapha and also reaches in all strotas and hence increases dhatu agni, deepan, pachan property. So, it is very much useful in allergic skin disorder.

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